

SMILE

**Supporting Mental health in young
People: Integrated Methodology
for cLinical dEcisions and evidence-
based interventions**

**This project has received funding from the European Union
Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Programme, under
Grant Agreement No°101080923**

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Consortium Partners

EU contributions: 6,018,376.25€

Start date: 1 May 2023

End date: 31 October 2026

Duration: 42 months

Consortium: 15 partners from 9 countries

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SMILE Workpackage Structure

FTK - Forschungsinstitut für Telekommunikation und Kooperation e. V. was founded in 1991 and acts as a supporting institution and coordinator of various projects for the state, the federal government and the European Union, but also for private companies. The FTK acts as an objective consulting institution with a sound research background and technical expertise and helps to initiate and realise information technology innovations, projects and cooperations.

In SMILE, FTK is leading the coordination of the project. Also, it is responsible for the development of the KM-EP and the control access via the SAPL tool.

The French innovative SME RDIUP, created in 2018, is specialized in the development of smart APIs, AI-based tools, and web-based platforms in various sectors (health, energy, mobility and FOF).

In the SMILE project, RDIUP will lead the communication, business models and exploitations activities and will develop the data analytics module, rewarding system, and Awareness mobile APP.

Also, it defines sustainable models and strategies for the exploitation and dissemination of innovative solutions.

INTRAS Foundation is a non-profit entity created in 1994 that, with a team of almost 600 professionals, helps people with mental health problems recover their life projects.

In SMILE, INTRAS is responsible for establishing a public network with local stakeholders in Spain and implementing a specific pilot to test the digital solutions.

INTRAS (INT) is a non-profit organisation dedicated to health and social-health care in the field of mental health, ageing and disability..

SWPS University excels in exploring the human mind and applying this expertise to address practical challenges of today and tomorrow. Also, SWPS University is a leading higher education institution in Poland, excelling in Psychology, Law, Language Studies, Literature and Culture Studies, Media and Communication Studies, Management, and Design.

In SMILE, SWPS is responsible for establishing a public network with local stakeholders in Poland and implementing a specific case study to test the digital solutions.

 Maribor, Slovenia

Univerza v Mariboru

The University of Maribor is the second largest and second oldest university in Slovenia with a long tradition. During these years, it became a successful scientific institution, the primary mission and guiding principle of which is the dissemination and enrichment of knowledge. It is rapidly developing new areas of activity, testing new study methods and seeking new ways of integrating with its environment.

In SMILE, UoM is responsible for the development of the Self-Assessment and Monitoring Framework (SAMF) and interactive chatbot.

<https://www.um.si/>

@Univerza_v_Mariboru

izidor.mlakar@um.si

 Barcelona, Spain

NVISION was created in 2006 in the Region of Barcelona, Spain. NVISION brings R&D to the market and develop innovative solutions using IoT, Big Data, Artificial Intelligence, Cloud and Edge Computing Architectures, and related technologies for advanced monitoring, prediction and management of complex systems, supporting the digitalization of different sectors, such as Energy and Health.

In SMILE, NVISION is responsible for the development of the Decision Support System (DSS). Also, It will integrate and host all modules in the Open Knowledge Platform (OKP).

<https://nvision.es/>

@nvisioniot

info@nvision.es

Köln, Germany

Nurogames is an independent game development and software engineering company founded in 2006 in Cologne/Germany. Nurogames develops gaming and serious games solutions for consumers and for the industry. Nurogames covers the entire value chain of game development - from the initial idea to the final product - for all major mobile, web, PC, console, VR, AR and XR platforms with a track record of more than 14 years.

In SMILE, Nurogames is responsible for the development of the gamified scenarios and gamification engine. Also, It will lead and coordinate the activities in WP4.

<https://www.nurogames.com/>

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Maribor, Slovenia

MESTNA OBČINA MARIBOR
UNIVERZITETNO MESTO MARIBOR

Municipality of Maribor (MOM) regular activities include among others also education, sport, health and social care. MOM is responsible for health and social welfare, for social security, health protection and family matters, elderly care, etc. The Office for Education, Health, Social Welfare and Research performs work and tasks in the field of preschool education, elementary school, music education, adult education as well as public health care.

In SMILE, MOM is responsible for establishing a public network with organizations and public health care service providers and implementing use case activities. MOM is promoting preventive programs in the field of mental health protection.

<https://maribor.si/>

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C.I.P. Citizens In Power (CIP) is non-profit, NGO. CIP constitutes one of the leading organizations in Cyprus in the fields of global education, social innovation, entrepreneurship, STEM and sustainable growth. Our team designs and implements cross-sectoral, interdisciplinary approaches as a response to social, educational and environmental challenges and policy gaps by employing technology transfer and operationalizing the research findings

In SMILE, CIP is responsible for establishing a large network with stakeholders and public organizations to build SMILE community. CIP will mainly promote preventive programs in migrant centers.

 <https://citizensinpower.org>
 [@citizensinpower](#)
 info@citizensinpower.org
natasa.a@citizensinpower.org

WIZ Research (WIZ) is an SME from Romania specialized in complex systems and deep tech with a unique combination of expertise in dynamic data ontologies, artificial intelligence staking and human-centered interfaces. Their know-how has been validated through large R&D projects, commercial services and tech-transfer activities. For SMILE, WIZ will lead the activities related to data operations and contribute to digital integrations, artificial intelligence and smart extensions.

In SMILE, WIZ is leading the WP6 activities and the development of middleware and data harmonisation and integration.

 <https://www.wizresearch.com/>
 [@WIZ_research](#)

Bologna, Italy

In SMILE, IRCCS-AOUBO is leading WP2 and is responsible for stakeholder analysis, literature review, and clinical studies definition. Also, It will provide a case study in Italy to assess the developed solutions.

- <https://www.aosp.bo.it/>
- @IRCCS_Bologna
- vincenza.frisardi@aosp.bo.it

The IRCCS Azienda Ospedaliero-Universitaria di Bologna - Policlinico di Sant'Orsola (IRCCS-AOUBO) is the first inter-company scientific hospitalization and care Institution in Emilia-Romagna (North of Italy) and has been identified as one of the best hospitals in Italy. IRCCS-AOUBO is a vibrating, high-standard care organization that works in a multidisciplinary and sophisticated network. It promotes skills and knowledge to deal with critical health demand and the governance of complexity.

Heidelberg, Germany

The Department of General Internal Medicine and Psychosomatics is the oldest psychosomatic hospital in Germany and stands for psychosomatic medicine and psychotherapy at the highest level. The department is integrated with wards and outpatient clinics in both the Center for Internal Medicine and the Center for Psychosocial Medicine of the University Hospital. This offers excellent opportunities for therapeutic care of the entire spectrum of diseases that arise from the interaction of body, mind and social factors.

In SMILE, UKH is leading the WP7 “Piloting and evaluation”. Also, It is responsible for the pilot study in Germany to assess the gamified solutions and the analytic results.

- <https://www.heidelberg-university-hospital.com/>
- @Heidelberg_university_hospital
- Gwendolyn.Mayer@med.uni-heidelberg.de

 Edinburgh, UK

THE UNIVERSITY
of EDINBURGH

The University of EDINBURGH (UoE) is one of the largest and most successful universities in the UK. Its international character is reflected in its international student population, international staff and in its joint research and other links with overseas universities, institutes, companies and governments. The University is the leading research university in Scotland and is amongst the top five in the United Kingdom.

In SMILE, UoE will contribute to the definition and assessment of the case study in UK. Also, it will define the societal and environmental wellbeing potential.

<http://www.ed.ac.uk>

[@The_University_of_Edinburgh](#)

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 Edinburgh, UK

Heriot-Watt University has five campuses: three in the UK (Edinburgh, Scottish Borders, and Orkney), one in Dubai and one in Malaysia. The University offers a highly distinctive range of degree programmes in the specialist areas of science, engineering, design, business, and languages. With a history dating back to 1821, Heriot-Watt University has established a reputation for world-class teaching and practical, leading-edge research, which has made it one of the top UK universities for business and industry.

In SMILE, HWU is leading the WP3 “Monitoring of Ethics, Security and Privacy” and contribute to the gamification development. Also, it will define and assess the case study in UK.

<https://www.hw.ac.uk/>

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Bologna, Italy

ALMA MATER STUDIORUM
UNIVERSITÀ DI BOLOGNA

The University of BOLOGNA (UniBo), founded nine centuries ago, stands as the oldest university in the Western world. Renowned for its history intertwined with great names in science and literature. Committed to sustainability values, UniBo prioritises territory preservation, community wellbeing, a knowledge-based economy, social equity, and effective collaboration for the common good. UniBo is among the top 5 Italian universities in major international rankings.

In SMILE, UniBo will be responsible for the Italian focus group, actively contribute to defining and assessing the case study in Italy, organise workshops, and play a key role in the pilot implementation phase.

<https://www.unibo.it/it>

[@università-di-bologna](#)

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Project contacts

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